

Efficiency of urea applied to rice by various methods

Amanullah Bhatti, Habibur Rehman, and Akbar Hussain Gurmani, Agricultural Research Station, Tarnab, Peshawar, Pakistan

Efficiency of urea applied to rice by different methods was studied at Dera Ismail Khan District, northwest frontier

province of Pakistan. The field experiments were conducted for 2 years on soil with 48% clay, 15% CaCO₃ low organic matter content (0.51%), and a pH of 7.9. Urea was applied at 120 kg N/ha at transplanting. A basal dose of 35 kg P/ha was applied as single superphosphate (9% P). IR6 was grown.

Results for grain yield were highly significant (see table). The highest paddy yield (7.3 t/ha) was obtained when urea

was incorporated into dry soil before flooding. All fertilizer treatments increased the yields significantly over the control. Wet soil application gave lower yield than dry soil application.

Dry soil urea incorporation also produced the highest straw yield and panicles per square meter, and gave highest net return per hectare and value cost and response ratio. □

Effect of urea application methods on rice yield.^a

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		Increase (t/ha) over no urea		Value cost ratio (VCR) ^b	Grain nutrient ratio	Panicles (no./m ²)	1,000-grain wt (g)
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw				
No urea	3.6	5.7	—	—	—	—	269	21.8
Urea broadcast on dry soil before flooding	6.2	11.1	2.6	5.4	6.49	21.41	496	22.8
Urea broadcast on dry soil before last planking	6.5	10.7	2.9	5.0	7.24	24.81	514	22.5
Urea incorporated in dry soil before flooding	7.3	12.8	7.7	7.1	9.51	31.08	527	22.8
Urea added in furrows in dry soil before flooding	7.0	11.3	3.4	5.6	8.54	28.16	527	23.2
Urea broadcast in paddy water before transplanting	5.3	8.5	1.7	2.8	4.32	14.25	391	22.5

^a Av of 2-year results. Results of individual years were significant, but analysis of combined data was not done. ^b Value of rough rice = US\$122.5/t; cost of urea fertilizer = US\$48.52/120 kg N. Value of straw is not included in the VCR.

Effect of neem cake on azolla growth and nitrogen fixation

S. Kannaiyan, M. Thangaraju, and G. Obilisami, Agricultural Microbiology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641 003, Tamil Nadu, India

Azolla is a free-floating nitrogen-fixing fern that plays an important role in the rice soil ecosystem. During January 1982, a field experiment in randomized block design with three replications measured the effect of neem cake on azolla growth and multiplication. Plots were prepared and neem cake at 25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150, 175, and 200 kg/ha was applied. *Azolla pinnata* (CBE strain) was inoculated at 200 g/m² and allowed to grow for 20 days. Azolla fresh weight per plot was recorded.

Neem cake significantly increased azolla growth at all application levels (see table). Azolla growth increased with increased neem cake application,

and neem reduced *Pyralis* sp. pest infestation considerably. In a pot experiment, azolla was grown with neem cake at 250

to 3,000 ppm levels. Azolla nitrogenase activity and chlorophyll content increased significantly.

Effect of neem cake on *A. pinnata* growth in the field, Tamil Nadu, India, 1982.

Neem cake (kg/ha)	Mean azolla yield (kg/3×2 m plot)	% increase over control	Doubling time (days)
Control	4.22	—	11.02
25	6.91	63.74	7.92
50	8.22	94.78	7.20
75	8.28	96.20	7.18
100	8.37	98.34	7.18
125	9.26	117.43	6.78
150	10.91	158.53	6.30
175	10.25	142.89	6.46
200	10.81	164.70	6.36

C. D. = 2.142
(C. D: P = 0.01)

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.